

Climate impacts on protein production: Building resilience through low-input winter- or spring-sown pulse-based mixtures.

Problem

Climate change impacts is causing unpredictable and extreme weather across Europe. Assuring protein yield potential demands adaptive cropping strategies

Solution

To use winter- and spring-sown mixtures, harvested either as grain or whole crop (silage) - depending on the climatic effects experienced.

Benefits

Protein yield is safeguarded using whole-crop, when grain yields may be compromised., although use of whole-crop may be limited to consumptions by ruminants. Benefits are therefore easier to realise in mixed farming systems (e.g., which include cows, and sheep); and/or where whole crop 'biorefining' is used.

Applicability box

Theme
Protein yield resilience.

Keywords
Protein; yield; resilience; grain; whole-crop.

Context
Arable and mixed-farm systems.

Required time
Growing season, whether spring- or winter-sown mixtures.

Period of impact
On growing season, post-harvest and post-harvest seed or whole-crop preparation.

Specialist Equipment: Not necessary.

Best used in: Cropped systems affected by a limited growing season, due to climate change impacts.

Practical recommendation

- High protein yields were obtained using either:
 - winter-sown faba (field) bean and wheat harvested as whole-crops; or,
 - spring-sown pea and wheat harvested as grain.
- The protein yields were up to 2x that achieved by average monocrops.
- Highest protein yields were obtained without synthetic nitrogen fertiliser use (50 kg/ha avoided).

The table below provides species, varietal and yield data for the top performing crop-mixtures.

Sown Crop-types, Species (Cultivars)	Total Yield / Protein Yield (t/ha) Yield type, biomass, (Protein t/ha, %)	Crop-Mixture Options			Fertiliser use (50 kg N/ha)
		Pea	Faba	Wheat	
Winter-faba bean & -wheat (Tundra, or Pantani & Skyscraper)	Whole Crop, 12-15 (1.2-1.9, 13 %)	No	Yes	Yes	No
Spring-pea & -wheat (Orchestra & WPB Escape) (faba = cv. Yukon)	Grain, 8-10 (1.7-1.9, 19 %)	Yes	(Yes)	Yes	No
<p>For comparison: grain protein yields of monocrops, estimated from UK yield averages (@15% moisture):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - faba bean: winter, or spring-sown, yield 3.6/3.5 t/ha (respectively), @28% protein = 0.85 t/ha (dry weight) - pea: spring-sown, yield 3.2 t/ha, @22.5 % protein = 0.61 t/ha (dry weight) - wheat: winter/spring, yield 5.7/9.0 t/ha, @12.5 % protein = 0.96 t/ha (dry weight) 					

Options in brackets were not found to be essential for protein yield resilience.
Fertiliser weight of nitrogen (N) from avoided use of ammonium nitrate.

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About this practice abstracts

Publisher: James Hutton Institute (JHI)

Author: Prof. Pietro P.M. Iannetta (JHI)

Contact: pete.iannetta@hutton.ac.uk;
piannetta@ucp.pt

Review: Dr Fanny Tran, Dr Chrizelle Krynauw, Sam Holden (JHI) and Dr Thomas Wilkinson (ADAS)

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